

The Kinetics of the Intramolecular Transformation of Ammonium Thiocyanate to Thiourea and Thiourea to Ammonium Thiocyanate.

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The decomposition of nitrogen pentoxide in the gaseous state has now been proved to be a perfectly homogeneous unimolecular reaction. The existence of unimolecular reactions in liquids has been doubted on the grounds that very little is known about the liquid state of matter which is very complex and that molecules in liquids are very much subject to attractions by neighbouring molecules. But, whether or not real unimolecular reactions can exist in liquids should be decided only by experimental study. Lueck (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **44**, 757) has found that the decomposition of nitrogen pentoxide dissolved in carbon tetrachloride and chloroform proceeds with almost the same velocity as in the pure gaseous state and that the influence of solvent in this particular case is very small. This would mean that unimolecular reactions may well take place even in solution. The recent work of Watson (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1925, **408**, 132) on the decomposition of derivatives of oxalacetic ester again lends support to the view that reactions of the first order may be met with in pure liquids. The present work was undertaken to see how far an isomeric transformation which takes place in the pure liquid state can conform to the ideal of a unimolecular reaction.

Waddell (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1898, **2**, 586) first investigated the kinetics of the transformation of ammonium thiocyanate to thiourea and showed in an approximate way that it was a reversible reaction of the first order. Atkins and Werner (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, **99**, 1167) also found the reaction to be of the first order. The experimental work of Waddell was admittedly not accurate and the study of velocity by Atkins and Werner was confined to only one temperature. Their results, however, point to one fact that the products of reaction in both the direct and reverse reactions

have no influence on the velocity of the reaction. From the standpoint of the present investigation, what is of importance is the study of the temperature coefficient of the reaction rates. The work of Waddell and Atkins and Werner has therefore been revised with such improvements as were found necessary and possible and extended over a wide range of temperature.

In gaseous reactions to prove whether a reaction proceeds homogeneously or whether surface effects come into play, the reactions are caused to take place over inert surfaces and surface area per unit mass of reacting substance altered. In liquid systems this test can be applied only to a small degree. The reactions described in this paper were tested in this way by introducing into the reaction vessels strips of platinum and glass wool prepared of Jena glass.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The ammonium thiocyanate and thiourea used in this work were each twice recrystallised from alcohol. During the course of the work it was found that the removal of the last traces of alcohol from the crystals was necessary to prevent the formation of some foul smelling products. These were formed perhaps by side reactions in small quantities which, however, did not affect the velocity of reaction. The last traces of alcohol were removed by heating the crystallised substances at 100° for a long time and then desiccating in vacuum for some days before use. Thiocarbamide purified as above was found to melt at 179° and never below that. This is in accordance with the prediction of Findlay (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 85, 402).

Two series of velocity measurements were made. In the first series almost equal quantities of ammonium thiocyanate and thiourea were introduced into a number of Jena glass bulbs which were then evacuated and sealed. Care was taken to see in all cases that traces of moisture, the substances might have absorbed during the filling of the bulbs, were completely removed by desiccation before sealing. About a dozen bulbs containing one of the substances at a time were put into a copper wire cage and immersed in an oil-thermostat of large capacity maintained at any desired temperature. The oil in the thermostat was kept well stirred and

the temperature kept very constant. The bulbs were taken out at intervals, suddenly chilled by dropping them into cold water; they were then thoroughly cleaned outside, broken and the contents analysed.

In the second series of experiments long Jena glass tubes ($1\frac{1}{2}$ " diameter and 12" long) sealed at one end and provided at the top with a side tube which could be connected to a phosphorous pentoxide bulb were used. About 20 grams of either ammonium thiocyanate or thiourea were put into a tube of this type, closed at the top with a rubber cork and kept immersed almost up to the neck in the thermostat. The object of connecting the side tube at the top with a P_2O_5 bulb was to keep the air in the tube as dry as possible during the experiment. Small quantities of the molten liquid were withdrawn in Jena glass pipettes at intervals, suddenly chilled and then analysed.

The velocity measurements made in these two series of experiments gave absolutely identical results.

When the experiments had to be carried on below the melting points of the substances, the tubes were first of all maintained for a short time a little above the melting points of the substances when they melted and a certain amount of transformation took place. This lowered the melting point and then the tubes were transferred to the thermostat.

The effect of surfaces (as stated above) was tested by introducing platinum strips and Jena glass wool into the tubes used in the second series of experiments. Unfortunately it has not been possible to study the effect of solvents on the velocity as it has not been possible to get a convenient solvent which dissolves both the substances and is not volatile at temperatures when the reaction begins to proceed at measureable rates.

Method of Analysis.—The estimation of thiourea and ammonium thiocyanate in the presence of each other is a matter of considerable difficulty. After many trials the following procedure which gave excellent results was finally adopted. Thiourea was estimated in the mixture iodimetrically as recommended by Reynolds and Werner (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 83, 1) and modified by Werner (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 99, 2166). The solution just before titration was diluted such that the amount of thiourea present in 250 c. c. never exceeded 0.02 gm. Titration of a mixture of ammonium

thiocyanate and thiourea against mercuric nitrate solution in presence of dilute nitric acid using ferric nitrate as indicator gives a reading corresponding to thiocyanate plus thiourea in the mixture (Williams Lunge's *Technical Methods of Chemical Analysis*, p. 656). This method was first tested for mixtures of known composition, and finally adopted when it was found to give very reliable results. In all cases both thiourea and thiourea plus thiocyanate were estimated and the percentage composition calculated.

Equilibrium between Thiourea and Ammonium Thiocyanate.

For the calculation of the velocity constants it is necessary to know the equilibrium concentrations of the constituents in the reaction mixture. Burrows (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 46, 1628) has studied the equilibrium of this system at different temperatures. It was thought desirable, however, to redetermine the equilibrium constant at the different temperatures at which velocity measurements were made.

The equilibrium was, at each temperature, approached from both sides. Table I gives the composition of the equilibrium mixtures, the equilibrium constants $k = \frac{\text{conc. NH}_4\text{CNS}}{\text{conc. CS(NH}_2)_2}$, and the heats of reaction at different temperatures, as calculated from variation of equilibrium constants with temperature.

TABLE I.

Temp.	% Thiourea	k	Q(heat of reaction)
140°C	28.10	2.559	... 3271 calories ... 3235 " ... 3117 " ... 3074 " Mean 3174 "
150°	26.24	2.811	
160°	24.56	3.071	
170°	23.09	3.300	
180°	21.76	3.595	

Rate of Reaction.

In a reversible reaction of the first order

if we start with a gram molecules of A,

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = k_1(a-x) - k_2x \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

where k_1 and k_2 are the velocities of the opposing reactions. If ϵ be the equilibrium value of x , then $k_1(a-\epsilon) = k_2\epsilon$ so that (1) may be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dx}{dt} &= k_1(a-x) - k_2 \frac{(a-\epsilon)}{\epsilon} x \\ &= k_1 + k_2(\epsilon-x) \end{aligned}$$

If we were to start with a gram molecules of B instead of A, it can be shown that

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = k_1 + k_2(a-x)$$

so that for both the direct and reverse reactions we would get the same integration constant, *i.e.*, we get the same velocity constant from whatever direction we proceed. This, as pointed out by Waddell, forms a test for a reversible reaction of the first order. This condition is fulfilled in the reaction studied, as shown in Tables II, II(a), III and III(a) which contain the results obtained at 140° and 150°.

TABLE II.

Time in min.	% Thiourea.	$a-x$	$k_1 + k_2$
0	6.92	21.18	—
30	8.94	19.16	0.003842
60	10.72	17.38	0.003291
90	12.29	15.81	0.003243
120	13.97	14.13	0.003369
180	16.82	11.28	0.003496
240	19.19	8.91	0.003601
360	23.05	5.05	0.003381
∞	28.10	0.00	0.003389 Mean

TABLE II(a).

Time in min.	% Thiourea.	$a-x$	$k_1 + k_2$
0	62.10	34.0	—
30	58.79	30.69	0.003411
60	55.80	27.70	0.003411
90	52.82	24.72	0.003537
120	50.70	22.60	0.003399
150	48.50	20.45	0.003227
180	46.50	18.40	0.003406
∞	28.10		Mean 0.003365

TABLE III.

Time in min.	% Thiourea.	$a-x$	$k_1 + k_2$
0	4.189	22.07
15	7.126	19.11	0.009598
30	9.689	16.65	0.009884
45	11.347	14.89	0.008744
60	13.767	12.47	0.009506
75	16.382	9.86	0.010718
90	17.174	9.07	0.009869
∞	26.24		Mean 0.009696

TABLE III(a).

Time in min.	% Thiourea.	$a-x$	$k_1 + k_2$
0	52.95	26.71	—
15	49.34	23.10	0.009674
30	46.26	20.02	0.009605
45	43.42	17.18	0.009757
60	41.00	14.76	0.009874
75	39.25	39.01	0.009532
∞	26.24		Mean 0.009698

The difference between the two sets of values is within experimental error. k_1 represents the velocity constant for the direct

reaction $\text{NH}_4\text{CNS} \rightarrow \text{CS}(\text{NH}_2)_2$, and k_2 the velocity constant for the reverse reaction. From the equilibrium constants at different temperatures, k_1 and k_2 could be computed. Table IV contains the summary of data thus obtained between 140° and 180° .

TABLE IV.

Temp.	$k_1 \times 10^4$	$k_2 \times 10^4$
140°C	9.999	25.58
150°	25.27	70.93
160°	60.90	187.02
$160^\circ(a)$	62.10	190.71
$160^\circ(b)$	61.20	187.94
170°	140.07	476.43
180°	305.42	1097.98

$160^\circ(a)$ and $160^\circ(b)$ represent the results obtained with platinum and glass wool surfaces respectively; it will be seen that they are very much the same as without these surfaces.

In Table V are given the temperature coefficients for k_1 and k_2 , and the energies of activation of the two molecules at different temperatures. E_a refers to the heat of activation in calories.

TABLE V.

Temp.	Temp. coeff. (k_1)	$E_{1,1}$	Temp. coeff. (k_2)	$E_{1,2}$
140°C	2.53	32398 calories	2.77	35568 calories
150°		32185 "	2.63	35386 "
160°		31915 "	2.54	35717 "
170°		31248 "	2.10	33398 "
180°		Mean 31935 "	Mean 35016 "	

It will be noticed that the heat of reaction as calculated from equilibrium measurements (3174 cal.) is almost exactly equal to

the difference between the energies of activation of the two molecules (which is equal to 3081 cal.) as is to be expected theoretically.

Discussion of Results.

The equation developed by Dushman (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 43, 397) and Rideal (*Phil. Mag.*, 1920, 40, 461) for the velocity of a unimolecular reaction has the form

$$k = \frac{E}{Nh} e^{-\frac{E}{RT}}$$

where $E = Nhv$ represents the critical increment in energy or the energy of activation of the molecule. Velocity coefficients calculated with the help of this equation in the case of nitrogen pentoxide decomposition both in the gaseous state and in solution agree pretty well with the experimentally determined values. For purposes of calculation this equation may be written in the form

$$\log k = 10.0208 + \log E - \frac{E}{4.571 T}$$

In Table VI the calculated values for k_1 and k_2 are compared with the experimentally determined values (the observed values given in Table IV are here given, calculated for seconds).

TABLE VI.

Temp.	$k_1 \times 10^2$ (obs.)	$k_1 \times 10_1$ (cal.)	$k_2 \times 10^2$ (obs.)	$k_2 \times 10^2$ (cal.)
140°C	1.667	399	4.263	10.68
150°	4.212	1019	11.826	28.48
160°	10.150	2441	31.17	74.90
170°	23.345	5680	79.40	186.10
180°	50.803	12720	182.99	451.90

It is evident from the table that while the calculated values for k_1 are more than 200 times the observed values, the calculated values for k_2 are only 2.5 times the observed values. It may be pointed out

that a difference of about 500 calories in the energy of activation as measured by the temperature coefficient is sufficient to cause such differences between the calculated and observed values as has been found in the case of k_1 . It may therefore be said that in the case of the reverse reaction, *vis.*, $\text{CS}(\text{NH}_2)_2 \rightarrow \text{NH}_4\text{CNS}$, Dushman's equation predicts the velocity of reaction pretty accurately. One cannot of course expect the Dushman—Rideal equation to hold both for the direct and reverse reactions in a case like the present one, where at the same temperatures the two reactions have almost the same temperature coefficients and the equilibrium constant remains almost the same.

The assumption in the Dushman—Rideal equation is the same as that in Lewis and Perrin's radiation hypothesis that $E = Nh\nu$, which means that a molecule to reach the active state absorbs one quantum of radiation of frequency ν . Calculations made on this basis predict absorption bands for molten ammonium thiocyanate and thiourea at 0.891 μ and 0.812 μ respectively. Unfortunately this could not be experimentally verified owing to the difficulty in dealing with these molten substances in infra-red spectroscopy.

The values of $\log k$ plotted against the reciprocals of absolute temperatures give for both the direct and reverse reactions very good straight lines. This is in accordance with the demands of the Arrhenius equation,

$$\log_{10} k = \frac{E}{2.3 RT} + B.$$

In Table VII are given the values of B , calculated for each temperature for k_1 and k_2 .

TABLE VII.

Temp.	$B (k_1)$	$B (k_2)$
140°C	12.14	14.17
150°	12.14	14.10
160°	12.14	14.10
170°	12.14	14.12
180°	12.14	14.09
	Mean 12.14	Mean 14.10

$$\frac{Ek_1}{B} = 2680$$

$$\frac{Ek_2}{B} = 2483$$

These constants as well as $\frac{E}{B}$ are almost the same as for many

other reactions (*cf.* Watson, *loc. cit.*).

According to Christiansen and Kramers (*Zeit. physikal. Chem.*, 1928, 104, 451) this constant $B = \log_{10} A$ where $1/A$ represents what they call the 'active life' of the molecule. On this basis the active lives of NH_4CNS and $\text{CS}(\text{NH}_2)_2$ molecules are 7.24×10^{-12} and 8×10^{-12} seconds respectively. Whereas Christiansen and Kramers find that in most cases this is of the order of 10^{-14} seconds.

Summary and Conclusion.

The kinetics of the intramolecular transformation, $\text{NH}_4\text{CNS} \rightleftharpoons$

$\text{CS}(\text{NH}_2)_2$ has been studied over the range 140–180°C. It has been found that the velocity of reaction in either direction is not affected by the presence of air, or by platinum and glass surfaces. Even the presence of slight traces of alcohol and moisture in the substances, although they produce small quantities of foul smelling substances, have no influence on the velocity of reaction. So far as the results of the present investigations go, the reaction appears to proceed in a perfectly reversible unimolecular manner.

Equilibrium between NH_4CNS and $\text{SC}(\text{NH}_2)_2$, has been studied over the range 140–180°C. It has been found that the heat of reaction as calculated from equilibrium data is exactly equal to the difference between the heats of activation of the two molecules. This is in accordance with theory.

The Dushman—Rideal equation gives values in good agreement with observed values for the velocity constant of the reaction $\text{CS}(\text{NH}_2)_2 \rightarrow \text{NH}_4\text{CNS}$ but not for the reverse reaction.

The constant B for the reaction has been calculated for both the reactions. These values are in good agreement with the values known for other reactions. From the standpoint of Christiansen

and Kramer's views, the active lives of the two molecules, NH_4CNS and $\text{CS}(\text{NH}_2)_2$, have been calculated and found to be 7.24×10^{-12} and 8×10^{-12} seconds respectively.

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